

Cloud of Mobile Small-cells for Higher Data-rates and Better Energy-efficiency

Ayman Radwan, Jonathan Rodriguez

Instituto de Telecomunicações,
Campus Universitário de Santiago,
3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal
{aradwan, jonathan} @ av.it.pt

Abstract—New mobile applications are pushing the limits on the requirements of mobile networks. Higher data rates, larger volume of data and lower latency are among the requirements of future networks. Toward those goals, we propose a new architecture to provide higher data rates, supporting large number of devices, at lower cost and better energy consumption ratings. The architecture is based on forming a cloud of on-demand mobile small cells, using user equipment or remote radio units. The cloud of mobile small cells is connected to the mobile network through a wireless high-speed front-haul, built on network-coding and cooperative communications. Due to continuous variation in network conditions, the cloud of mobile small cells is self-organizing. Security issues are highlighted and counter mechanisms are discussed.

Keywords— *Small-cells; self-organizing networks; network coding; security; mobile cloud;*

I. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid penetration of advanced smart mobile applications and the nature of such applications, the requirements of wireless mobile networks are tightening. Higher data rates, lower latency and larger capacity are just the natural evolution for network requirements. Moreover, ubiquity, lower energy consumption for extended lifetime of device batteries and autonomous network management are some examples of additional requirements putting more pressure on mobile networking design. Fortunately, 4G networks, which have been and are still being deployed worldwide, have achieved lots of progress towards meeting those requirements, especially in terms of higher data rates. Despite those advancements, the foreseen increase in number of connected wireless mobile devices, along with the expected high data volumes, makes it hard for current networking concepts to keep up with future network requirements.

Multiple networking forecasts have predicted a huge increase in number of connected devices, mainly due to the vast adoption of machine-to-machine (M2M) communications, within the Internet of Things (IoT) concept [1], [2]. The surge in the number of wirelessly connected devices will continue, reaching up to 100 times, with mobile data volume increasing to 1000x times current volumes [2], [3]. Moreover, the volume of mobile data will continue to increase. The traffic from wireless and mobile communications will finally surpass that originating from wired device by 2019 [1]. The amount of data and the

number of connected devices will not be the only burden on future mobile networks. Additionally, the nature of the applications, with the adoption of IoT and high resolution videos (4K and Virtual Reality), will add new burdens to the networking requirements. Data rates will reach new highs, foreseen to be 10 to 100 times that of 4G [4]. New applications, including e-Health and critical mission applications, are increasing the burden on accepted latency. With such type of application, latency, as low as 1ms end-to-end, will have to be accommodated [5].

All those stringent requirements have led for a common acceptance between worldwide researchers and main players in telecommunications, that incremental advancements of current networking (4G) will not be able to meet future networking requirements by 2020 [5]. This has led to the worldwide acceptance of the need for a new mobile networking paradigm. This has come to be known as the Fifth Generation (5G). It has to be elaborated here, that 5G has not yet been standardized and is not expected to hit the market before 2020. Despite that, many technology trends have been widely accepted to form part of the upcoming 5G paradigm and are treated as such within the research community.

In this paper, we work with that in mind, building on such technology trends to provide a new network architecture capable of achieving higher data rates, at low energy consumption, without the need for high investment. The concept of low cost solution is very appealing nowadays, at a time where network operators are reluctant to invest much in new solutions, for fear of them becoming obsolete once 5G is enrolled. Moreover, building our solution based on technology trends widely foreseen to be integrated within the 5G solution encourages more operators to adopt such solution.

Our proposed solution aims to narrow the gap between currently adopted networking technologies and the foreseen requirements of 2020 networking, by using technology trends widely accepted to be part of the 5G paradigm to deliver higher capacity and data rates, lower cost per bit, enhanced energy efficiency, while supporting new services with different nature. The solution builds on the notion of on-demand mobile small cells. Such mobile small cells can be setup on the run, based on demand, using user equipment or remote radio units (RRUs). Another dimension of innovation is the provision of wireless

front-haul using network coding and cooperative communications, to provide high-speed reduced-cost energy-efficient connectivity to mobile small cells. With such random and highly variable environment, the management of such concept becomes too complicated and the sustainability of optimal operating point requires continuous modification of the network topology and location of mobile small cells; hence self-organizing networking becomes the natural evolution of network management and is clearly an integral part of our proposed solution. The proposed solution, hence, provides a cloud of mobile small cells, wirelessly connected to the core network through high-speed front-haul, and offering high data rate, larger capacity, and better energy efficiency to network operators at low cost.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II presents an overview of the defined 5G use-cases and its anticipated technology trends. Section III introduces the overall architecture of the proposed solution. The front-haul part of the solution is addressed in Section IV, while Section V discusses the cloud of mobile small cells. Section VI highlights the security issues raised, based on such disruptive solution. Section VII concludes the paper.

II. 5G USE-CASES AND TECHNOLOGY TRENDS

This section draws a picture of what future networks, by 2020 and beyond, will look like, along with the predicted winning technology trends, that are highly accepted by the telecommunications research and stakeholder community to form part of such highly anticipated concept.

We start by the vision of 5G networks, through the definition of the main three use-cases of 5G, as predicted by 3GPP and ITU [6], [7]. The future network is foreseen to include multiple heterogeneous scenarios and use-cases, which are so hard to list all in one document. Based on that, the scenarios envisioned to exist in the future networks (i.e. 5G era) were mainly divided into three main categories, namely [6], [7]:

- **Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB):** This use-case represents the natural evolution and extension of current networking, basically providing higher speeds for already existing applications, such as streaming, high quality video and virtual reality. It is worth mentioning that this use-case mainly addressed human-centric applications, in contrast to the other two use-cases, below.
- **Massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC):** This use-case addresses the foreseen future of IoT, which envisions very large number of connected devices, which have to be characterized by low cost, enhanced coverage and long battery lifetime. This use-case targets applications, which are delay-tolerant. With the vast adoption of IoT, massive number of sensors are expected to be deployed all around us.
- **Ultra-Reliable and Low Latency Communications (URLLC):** This use-case is also known as critical machine-type communications (cMTC). The applications, targeted by this use-case, possess stringent requirements, including ultra-

low latency and availability. The use-case is mainly defined to enable mission-critical applications, drone control, and self-driving cars (to say a few examples). This type of applications is considered the main driver for 5G and the hardest requirements to achieve. On the other hand, they are considered the applications, which will deliver the greatest social benefits [7].

As can be seen from the definition of the use-cases, each use-case has one main requirement. eMBB is mainly concerned with high data-rates, while the main characteristic of mMTC is the huge amount of foreseen transmitted data, due to the massive number of connected devices envisioned in this scenario. Alternatively, the killer characteristic of URLLC (cMTC) use-case is the ultra-low latency and high reliability. Based on that, the three use-cases can be positioned on the vertices of a triangle, as in Figure 1. Different applications and use-cases are then placed within the triangle, to reflect their characteristics and requirements based on their proximity to each vertex (i.e. use-case). As can be seen in the figure, self-driving cars are positioned so close to URLLC, while high quality video is close to eMBB, but still not so close, and is a bit towards URLLC, since it still needs low latency. Smart city is obviously the main application of mMTC, and is basically the main driver of huge number of connected devices.

Figure 1. 5G Scenarios and applications

Based on this use-cases definition, a clear picture of future networking can be drawn. The mobile network of 2020 and beyond needs to support a huge number of devices, requiring high data-rates, producing outrageous amount of data, and sometime it is necessary to support ultra-low latency for critical mission.

Towards achieving such goals, 5G research is going on a fast track to provide the characteristics of the future networking. Although 5G is not yet standardized and 5G systems are not foreseen before 2020, the research community along with the main stakeholders and players in the field have collectively accepted certain technologies to play a part of the 5G paradigm. As a start, the 5G networks are widely accepted to be highly densified, with different types of cells (macro, pico, small, etc.), integrating legacy networks (3G and 4G) with new 5G. Cloud-based radio access network (C-RAN) will definitely play a main role in 5G, along with cooperation, network virtualization and network slicing [8].

Figure 2. Overall system architecture

Moreover, as mentioned before, with the complex nature of future networks and their high variability, automated management of networks has to be accommodated within the new 5G paradigm; hence self-organizing networks will play a major role in 5G [8]. These technology trends present some of the most accepted trends to form part of 5G, which have been integrated in our proposed solution to provide a cloud of self-organizing mobile small cells. It is worth noting that we are not claiming to draw the exact picture of 5G paradigm; instead, we are just highlighting the widely accepted technology trends that have been used in building our solution.

III. OVERALL SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Our proposed architecture of mobile small-cells is built on technology trends, such as densification of networks, cooperation, and self-organizing networks. The proposed solution envisages a collection of mobile small cells covering the urban landscape. Such mobile small cells are considered to be virtual in nature, since they can be setup on-demand, at any place, at any time, using existing devices. Such devices can be user equipment or RRU. The main concept is that those mobile devices are connected wirelessly to the network, through a wireless high-speed front-haul. The wireless front-haul is foreseen to be formed using other mobile devices, through network-coding and cooperative communications. The foreseen overall architecture of the proposed solution is schematized in Figure 2. The proposed mobile small cells (can be called hotspots), from the end-user perspective, are the vehicle for experiencing a plethora of 5G broadband services at low cost with reduced impact on the lifetime of mobile devices. The mobile small cells cooperate to form a “wireless-network-of-mobile small cells” or “cloud of mobile small cells” that have several gateways/entry points to the mobile network using intelligent high-speed connections. In the next two subsections, we will list the details of the two main counterparts of the architecture, namely the wireless front-haul and the self-organizing network of mobile small cells.

IV. WIRELESS HIGH-SPEED FRONT-HAUL

Central to our proposed solution is the provision of a wireless high-speed front-haul towards the mobile small cells. The envisioned front-haul can be realized using multiple technology options. To start, the basic solution can be the mobile small cell directly connected to an existing eNB. Such solution can be employed, if capacity allows, meaning with low number of deployed mobile small cells. With the foreseen huge number of connected devices, a big number of mobile small cells will be required. With high number of wireless mobile small cells, direct link with the eNB will result in a limit on the number of allowed deployed small cells, especially with the high resulting interference from such links.

In emerging heterogeneous networking environment, two communications technologies are playing a prominent role: cooperation, and small cells. The interplay between these can provide a solid building block for the mobile cell concept. Using the abundance of existing mobile devices in future dense networks, short-range cooperative communications among user devices can provide a footing for the energy and throughput gain required for 5G networks and services. The concept is further illustrated in Figure 3. The relays/helpers present existing mobile devices (can be user equipment, RRU or machine device), which cooperate together to form a wireless high-speed link to connect the mobile device acting as a small cell to the eNB. Moreover, the proposed solution enables the use of C-RAN architecture. It is worth mentioning that front-haul requires higher bandwidth and lower latency than backhaul. However this architecture results in more efficient use of RAN resources, and along with interference and mobility management tools, can significantly decrease interference in the network.

Those cooperative links will have to be secured, due to the potential sensitive data expected to be transmitted in future networks. Security issues are further discussed in Section VI.

Figure 3. A wireless high-speed front-haul using network-coding and cooperative communications

V. CLOUD OF SELF-ORGANIZING MOBILE SMALL CELLS

The proposed solution mainly aims at providing a new version of outdoor “femtocell” like mobile small cells, with their highly appreciated ratings in terms of achieved data-rates and energy efficiency. The solution moves beyond the current vision of small cells, through new mobile small cell paradigm, where end-users play the role of prosumers (provider/consumer) of wireless connectivity. A network of mobile small cells is envisioned in this solution. Those mobile small cells are interconnected in a network, forming a cloud of mobile small cells, with multiple gateways connected to the mobile network using a wireless high-speed front-haul, which has been discussed in the previous subsection.

Due to the continuous variation in the networking environment, the sustainability of optimal operating point becomes complicated; hence automated management of networks is essential in our proposed solution. We deploy self-organizing mobile small cells concept. Based on users’ location, their used applications and requirements, the network determines when and where a mobile small cell is required to be deployed. With the advancement in capabilities of networks and smart devices, user location and her/his current used applications can be easily retrieved. A context-aware architecture is integrated within the solution to analyze the locations and applications of users, and determine when a certain number of users are in the vicinity of each other, requiring the deployment of a new mobile small cell. The choice of which device to act as the clusterhead (small cell access point) is another challenge. It is clear that being a clusterhead drains the resources of the mobile device. For this reason, the role of a clusterhead/mobile small cell has to be rotated among multiple devices, to avoid draining the resources of one particular device. Additionally, not all mobile devices are suitable to act as a small cell. The choice of a certain device to act as a clusterhead takes into account multiple issues. The device has to have an abundance of resources, including memory to cache data, residual battery charge, and processing capabilities. Moreover, the chosen device has to be in a good location, with good connectivity to a big number of mobile devices, limiting the requirement for multiple small cells existing in nearby locations; hence decreasing interference between different mobile smalls. The system has to be intelligent enough to decide on its own (automated

management) when a mobile small cell is required, and which device should act as the clusterhead. Furthermore, the system is able to re-configure already existing mobile small cells to change their members, completely drop a certain mobile small cell, or switch the role of clusterhead to another device, based on variation in the networking environment.

In contrast to wireless front-haul, the connectivity within the mobile small cell can use short/medium range wireless options, such as WLAN (IEEE802.11) or even mmWave (if line-of-sight connectivity exists). Additionally, mobile devices can connect to the mobile using the same mobile communication technology, as the co-located eNB with little coordination due to the short-range of the connection (hence, little interference to other eNBs and other mobile small cells).

The different mobile small cells are interconnected among themselves, through high-speed links. Such links can be short-range cooperative communications, direct LTE (or 3G or 5G) links, or even mmWave links (if possible/LOS). Having this interconnection, the multiple interconnected mobile small cells form a cloud of mobile small cells, with high data rate connections to the mobile network through the high-speed front-haul or access to services/cloud services available within the cloud of mobile small cells. The envisioned cloud of mobile small cells is illustrated by Figure 4. It can be seen in the figure that the complicated details of the network is hidden from the end-users. For the end-users, the network appears as a cloud of available services.

Although the proposed solution is mainly advised to support high data-rates, large number of connected devices, and better energy ratings, at low cost, Figure 4 shows another dimension, where the solution can be used; namely device-to-device (D2D) communications. The solution goes beyond the current state-of-the-art by delivering multi-hop D2D communications with relatively acceptable low latency. Further investigation is required to clearly identify the adequate use-case for such scenario.

Again, it is worth mentioning here that security becomes too complicated, due to the existence of big number of mobile small cells, with data being transmitted among a number of devices, which may be owned by other users. Security is further discussed in next section.

Figure 4. Cloud of mobile small cells

VI. SECURITY

The proposed solution is innovative and goes beyond the current vision of small cells by 5G, which highlights multiple new research challenges in terms of investigating new heterogeneous networking topologies, architectures, along with new cooperative protocols and automated management. Lastly, security becomes an interesting topic, with such complicated networking nature.

In current and future mobile applications, security is becoming a critical topic. With the continuous adoption of new mobile applications, very sensitive information is transmitted over the network. This has resulted in a surge in cybercrime, ranging from high risk cases such as identity theft or hacking of personal information, down to the less dangerous network attacks such as pollution attacks or Denial of Service (DoS) attacks. Although network attacks are less dangerous in general, in the new networking era with critical mission applications, pollution attacks can still be expensive, if critical delay-sensitive information is not delivered on time.

Given that we employ network coding to form new energy efficient and high speed networking topologies for mobile small cells, security attacks, such as pollution attacks and Denial of Service (DoS) attacks, resulting in sever network performance degradation and energy waste are one of our main concerns. Towards this direction, the design and implementation of efficient secure network coding mechanisms and schemes to mitigate such attacks in the envisioned network-coding enabled mobile small cell network are included in the overall system. Specifically, the architecture integrates a secure network coding framework including i) integrity schemes against pollution attacks, ii) secure key management schemes for the integrity schemes, and iii) a collaborative intrusion detection and prevention mechanism to mitigate DoS and Distributed DoS (DDoS) attacks.

Furthermore, security of data has to be addressed in multiple dimension. First, secured efficient authentication schemes are required, with optional revocation for misbehavior. The design has to take into consideration how a mobile small cell would be able to authenticate a remote user to access its resources; whether authentication is performed locally at the small cell or back at the core network has to be determined. Second, security of transmitted data has to be guaranteed. Mobile small cells, as well as relays on the way towards the mobile network, should be able to decode transmitted data to verify correct reception, but should not be able to decode the sensitive transmitted information; hence secured network coding should be carefully implemented within the network of mobile small cells, as well as along the wireless high-speed front-haul.

VII. CONCLUSION

With the waves of new applications hitting the mobile networks, more tightened requirements are being enforced. Especially with the rapid adoption of IoT, and Smart city concept, the number of mobile devices is foreseen to multiply, along with a vast increase in the volume of transmitted data.

Another type of applications is mission-critical communications, such as drone control and self-driving cars. These applications require ultra-low latency, high reliability, and availability. Towards addressing those requirements, the paper proposed a new architecture based on a cloud of on-demand mobile small cells, to deliver high data-rate, support large number of devices, with good energy efficiency, at low costs. The solution deploys the notion of mobile small cell that can be setup on the run, based on network conditions. The main characteristic of such solution is the wireless high speed front-haul provided through network coding and cooperative communications towards the core network, built on top of a C-RAN architecture. The solution consists of a network of mobile small cells, interconnected through high-speed links, forming a cloud of mobile small cells. Such cloud is self-organizing. In an era, where cybercrime is a constant threat, security becomes a critical topic when designing any new networking architecture. Security issues within the proposed solution have been highlighted and foreseen counter mechanisms have been discussed. Implementation and evaluation of proposed solutions are planned for future work.

Acknowledgment

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement H2020-MSCA-ITN-2016 SECRET-722424.

Author Ayman Radwan would also like to acknowledge the financial support from FCT through the grant IF/01393/2015.

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